

ASSESSING FERTILISER OPTIONS FOR SUSTAINABLE MAIZE PRODUCTION IN AFRICA

Why organic fertilization?

Maize is a key crop in many African countries. There is a need for sustainable maize production due to growing food demand and declining soil fertility.

1 CONVENTIONAL AGRICULTURE

- High use of synthetic fertilizers, pesticides and herbicides
- Expansion of agricultural land area
- Increased specialization and monocultures
- Intensive tillage
- High yield focus

ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACTS 2

- Increases greenhouse gas emissions
- Depletes natural resources
- Reduces soil quality
- Reduces biodiversity
- Reduces ecosystem resilience

3 IMPACTS ON FUTURE AGRICULTURE

- Increased production costs
- Reduced future economic viability of farm businesses
- Potential negative effect on future provision of food

KEY MESSAGES

- Maize yields increase with all treatments
- All treatment options are profitable
- Profit is correlated with inflation
- The major limiting factor to organic fertilizer use is unavailability
- Organic fertilizer sustains soil health
- Organic fertilizer should be promoted for sustainable maize production in Africa
- Strategies to increase organic fertilizer production and usage should be pursued

APPROACH

- Field trials established to compare: 1) organic, 2) synthetic, and 3) Integrated organic and synthetic fertilizer treatments
- Collection of data on yields, prices, and costs of production
- Financial analysis of all three treatments over a 30 year time horizon

Yields and gross margins predicted over 30 years horizon

Returns on Labour (RoL), Benefit Cost Ratio (BCR) & Return on Investment (RoI)

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